

High-Frequency Structure of Displacement Responses at the Junction Between Outer Hair Cells and Deiters Cells Suggests Lineal Motion Patterns

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Abstract. Cochlear displacement responses measured using optical coherence tomography (OCT) are sensitive to the system's viewing angle relative to sample anatomy. As each measurement is a one-dimensional projection of motion onto the beam axis, the anatomical components of motion cannot be separated from single OCT measurements. One result of this is apparently disparate responses at the junction between outer hair cells and Deiters cells (OHC-DC) in the gerbil cochlea when measured at different viewing angles. These results can be synthesized by the knowledge that structures in the organ of Corti complex (OCC) are expected to move with displacement components in multiple anatomical directions. While it has been proposed that cell groups within the OCC move in the elliptical patterns expected for fluid motion, our data from the gerbil base indicate *lineal* motion in the longitudinal-transverse plane – a degenerate elliptical pattern with aspect ratio zero. Lineal motion explains features that appear in the responses measured with a substantial longitudinal axis – notches in the amplitude response and discontinuous lifts in the phase response. These features are unlikely to result from non-degenerate elliptical patterns, suggesting that OHC-DC does not move similarly to fluid. Thus, longitudinal motion must arise from other mechanisms such as longitudinally slanted anatomical structures in the OCC (e.g. the phalangeal processes) or motion in intra-OCC fluid spaces that is distinct from that in the scalae.

INTRODUCTION

Optical coherence tomography (OCT) has led to many micromechanical findings within the organ of Corti complex (OCC), as the technology can resolve angstrom-scale displacements at a depth into the sample [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7]. OCT measures displacement along the beam axis, which means that data from single experiments are one-dimensional projections of the three-dimensional motions in the cochlea [8, 9]. This limits the interpretation of so-called uniaxial measurements, or measurements taken from a single beam axis angle.

OCT can be used to *quantitatively* probe two- or three-dimensional motion by observing a structure at multiple beam axis angles and back-projecting the resultant displacement measurements [10, 11, 12, 13]. This back-projection method also requires registration of measured points in the OCC, which has been performed in various ways depending on the constraints of the experiment.

Other *qualitative* methods for determining features of other components of motion involve the observation of points at distinct positions from distinct viewing angles, so that registration is not required [7, 14]. For example, very significant differences in relative phase responses between outer hair cell (OHC) and basilar membrane (BM) motion are seen when the OCT beam axis is pointed towards the apex in comparison to when it is pointed towards the base [2, 14]. Other interesting differences include magnitude notches and discontinuous phase lifts in the responses at the outer hair cell-Deiters cell (OHC-DC) junction, apparent at some viewing angles but not at others [7].

In this work, we show quantitative reconstructions of longitudinal and transverse components of motion (that is, two-dimensional motion) at OHC-DC in the base of the gerbil cochlea in response to 80 dB SPL stimuli. The reconstructions reveal that OHC-DC motion follows a very narrow elliptical path – almost a straight line, with towards-base motion in phase with towards-scala-media motion. This *lineal motion* indicates that the OHC-DC does not move similarly to fluid, which exhibits non-degenerate elliptical patterns. Figure 1 shows a cartoon cross-section of the OCC in the transverse-longitudinal plane through the OHC-DC region, along with the approximate line of motion seen in our results.

Lineal motion is useful in describing two qualitative features of displacement responses seen in uniaxial measurements. In particular, lineal motion predicts a half-cycle phase difference between measurements where the beam axis points sufficiently apically and those where the beam axis is more transverse or basal-pointing. It also predicts the existence of a viewing axis perpendicular to the line of motion at which a rapid phase lift and magnitude notch would be expected to occur. Both of these features are observable in uniaxially measured data; the former can be seen in [2,

FIGURE 1. Cartoon of a longitudinal-transverse cross-section of the OCC through OHC-DC, with longitudinal (L) radial (R) and transverse (T) directions labeled in the top-right. Motion is measured at OHC-DC along a longitudinal span, and the approximate line of motion was found to be in the direction shown by the blue arrows; that is, towards-base and towards-scala-media motion are approximately in phase. When accessing the 20–25 kHz best frequency region, the viewing axis can be nearly perpendicular to those arrows. BM = Basilar Membrane, OHC = Outer Hair Cells, DC = Deiters Cells, PP = Phalangeal Processes.

7, 14] and the latter is shown in the Results section of the present manuscript.

Our findings lend credence to feedforward models of cochlear mechanics, especially the area pump model of Guinan which predicts the same relative phases of longitudinal and transverse OHC-DC motion that we have measured [15]. The longitudinal component of motion is of similar magnitude (and at times larger than) the transverse component, and the direction of the line of motion suggests a potential energy transfer through the phalangeal processes (PP) of the Deiters cells.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

Young adult gerbils were anesthetized using ketamine and pentobarbital. The round window membrane (RWM) was exposed by excising tissue and making a small hole in the bulla, and the head was situated on a two-axis goniometer. The gerbil was placed under a Thorlabs Telesto III OCT system with an LSM03 5x objective lens so that the OCC could be seen through the RWM. A speaker tube was placed in the ear canal (EC) for delivery of sound stimuli, and a Sokolich ultrasonic microphone was used to monitor EC pressure.

Sound stimuli were zwuis tone complexes containing 25 frequency components, each with randomized phase between 0 and 2π radians. At regular intervals throughout the experiment, EC pressure in response to swept-tone stimuli was measured to assess the magnitudes of distortion product otoacoustic emissions (DPOAEs). These were used as a means to assess cochlear condition, and it was assured that their magnitudes did not fall significantly over the course of the experiment. Further details of animal preparation and experimental equipment are provided in *Strimbu et al., 2020* [16]. Experiments were approved by the Columbia University Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee.

To perform reconstructions of 2-D responses, we measured OCC displacements at two or more beam axis angles relative to the cochlear anatomy. Different viewing angles were achieved by rotating the gerbil's head using the goniometer without moving the OCT system. Anatomical angles were assessed using the method described in *Frost et al., 2022* [17], and it was ensured that negligible radial component was present. For both viewing angles, the OCT beam passed through the RWM, down the cochlear spiral to access the 20 – 25 kHz best frequency location. The two-dimensional motion was derived from the uniaxial OCT measurements using the methods of skew correction, registration and reconstruction described in *Frost et al., 2023* [11].

FIGURE 2. Transverse and longitudinal OHC-DC displacement gain with respect to EC pressure in response to 80 dB SPL zwuis tone complexes. Results are from three different animals. For reference, BM phase from the same longitudinal cross-section is shown for each data set.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Here we show (1) reconstructed longitudinal and transverse displacement responses that show near-linear motion, and (2) uniaxial displacement responses that exhibit one prediction of near-linear motion. Figure 2 shows longitudinal and transverse components of OHC-DC displacement responses to 80 dB SPL zwuis tone complexes from three animals. Features to note include transverse OHC-DC phase either lagging/matching BM phase across frequency, with longitudinal OHC-DC phase leading BM across frequency. The difference between OHC-DC longitudinal and transverse phase is very close to 0.5 cycles at all frequencies.

Figure 3 shows two examples of uniaxially measured OHC-DC data in which a phase lift manifests. In these experiments, the measurement axis had significant components in both the transverse and longitudinal directions. In the 80 dB SPL response, a phase lift is seen relative to the lower-level response, where the phase rapidly jumped by about 0.5 cycles. At the same time, a notch appeared in the magnitude. This signifies that at this viewing angle and SPL, from one frequency to the next, the motion went through the condition where it was nearly perpendicular to the viewing axis.

Inspired by the measured lineal motion of Figure 2, we will now develop a simple model of lineal motion which will turn out to predict the lift in the uniaxially measured data of Figure 3. We write the OHC-DC displacement in response to frequency f as $\mathbf{d}^o(f) = (d_l^o(f) \ d_t^o(f))^T \in \mathbb{C}^2$, written in its longitudinal and transverse components. We measure this motion with the beam axis making an angle of θ with the transverse axis. Writing the components in polar form (where \angle denotes the phase of the complex number and j is the imaginary unit), the motion measured along this axis is

$$\delta^o(f, \theta) = |d_l^o(f)| e^{j\angle d_l^o(f)} \sin \theta + |d_t^o(f)| e^{j\angle d_t^o(f)} \cos \theta. \quad (1)$$

The lineal model allows us to simplify this expression, as the phases of the components differ by exactly π radians.

FIGURE 3. Uniaxially recorded OHC-DC displacement data from Ge976 at 60 and 80 dB SPL at two distinct longitudinal locations, shown in the two columns. The measurement axis had significant components in both the transverse and longitudinal directions. In these data, a rapid phase lift is seen in the 80 dB response of about 0.5 cycles relative to the 60 dB SPL response.

That is,

$$e^{j\angle d_t^o(f)} = e^{j(\pi + \angle d_t^o(f))} = -e^{j\angle d_t^o(f)}, \quad (2)$$

$$\delta^o(f, \theta) = (|d_t^o(f)| \sin \theta - |d_t^o(f)| \cos \theta) e^{j\angle d_t^o(f)}. \quad (3)$$

Considering the absolute value case-wise, we arrive at two revealing equations:

$$|\delta^o(f, \theta)| = \left| |d_t^o(f)| \sin \theta - |d_t^o(f)| \cos \theta \right|, \quad (4)$$

$$\angle \delta^o(f, \theta) = \begin{cases} \angle d_t^o(f), & |d_t^o(f)| \sin \theta > |d_t^o(f)| \cos \theta \\ \angle d_t^o(f) = \angle d_o^l(f) + \pi, & |d_t^o(f)| \sin \theta < |d_t^o(f)| \cos \theta \end{cases}. \quad (5)$$

We have a “winner-takes-all” phase behavior in the uniaxial measurements, where the measured phase will be precisely that of the largest projected component. As the components’ magnitudes vary in frequency, viewing angles where the beam axis has significant components in both anatomical directions may have a different component dominating in Equation 5 at different frequencies. In other words, in a uniaxial measurement with both longitudinal and transverse components, there may exist a frequency f_{\perp} at which the case of Eqn 5 switches. This would correspond to a very rapid phase shift of a half-cycle, which is precisely what is seen in the data of Figure 3. The phase shift frequency would vary with stimulus level if the motion components display different amounts of nonlinear scaling.

On the other hand, in measurements where the beam axis is sufficiently transverse or sufficiently longitudinal, this type of case-switch would not occur. This explains why this characteristic phase lift is not seen in data measured with a transverse optical axis, in the very base of the cochlea. (A phase lift can occur with that optical axis, but it has a different character and occurs for a different reason [7].)

Mechanically, the presence of lineal motion is in line with feedforward models of cochlear energy transfer. The DCs connect to the reticular lamina (RL) through the apically-oriented microtubule-packed phalangeal processes (PP) and to the BM through the transverse-pointing Deiters stalk [18], so the region has architectural components in both

directions (see Figure 1). The measured responses suggest a particular push-pull behavior of these two structures that would expand the OCC area in one cross-section (through the apically slanted PPs) while contracting it in another.

This is in line with the work of Guinan [15], who developed an area pump model. In his model, there is a hinging motion at OHC-DC driven by the electromotile expansion and contracting of the OHCs, inducing a longitudinal component of motion in the apically-slanted PPs, which then push on the RL resulting in a longitudinally varying cross-sectional area. This would effectively pump fluid through the intra-OCC fluid ducts and transfer energy longitudinally. The model suggests the presence of lineal motion with OHC-DC longitudinal and transverse components one half-cycle out of phase with one another in precisely the directions measured here (see Figure 4 of Guinan, 2022 [15]).

CONCLUSIONS

We have shown that at moderately high stimulus levels, the OHC-DC exhibit a lineal motion pattern in line with the area pump model of the cochlea [15]. The data also explain a previously unexplained rapid phase lift seen in some OCT data where the axis has significant components in both the longitudinal and transverse directions.

Our reconstruction method is sensitive to noise, as measurements at sufficiently different angles are difficult to achieve through the RWM of gerbil. As such, our results are limited to fairly high SPL. It would be valuable to see if these results held at lower SPL. This could be facilitated by a preparation in which displacement measurements at more extreme viewing angles were possible, using the same method described in Frost *et al.*, 2023 [11].

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

Tianying Ren: How much viewing angle change could be achieved by rotating the gerbil's head using the goniometer without moving the OCT system?

Response: In the experimental preparation used to acquire the present data, a viewing angle change of at most 15 degrees has been achieved. This is primarily limited by the size of the round window opening. In other preparations, such as those where the tissue can be imaged through bone, the maximum viewing angle difference would likely be much larger.

Tianying Ren: How does the lineal motion in the longitudinal-transverse plane change with frequency?

Response: This varies by preparation, but it points in characteristically similar directions at all frequencies. However, relative magnitudes of the components vary (as seen in Figure 2) causing some change, but this change is not consistent across experiments.

Aleks Zosuls: Can I interpret lineal degenerate elliptical motion to mean the ellipse is flattened into a line?

Response: Yes, the motion is always elliptical, but (1) a line is technically a degenerate ellipse with aspect zero, and (2) the aspect ratios found here are not precisely zero so these are simply very narrow ellipses.

Anders Fridberger (*oral comment*): On our Thorlabs system we run calibrations measuring vibrations with a piezo stack and an artificial target with similar reflectivity as the organ of Corti on top. What we found was that the Thorlabs system has a tendency of making half-cycle errors when the signal level is low. This affects maybe between 1% and 5% of pixels depending on the level of displacement that you are measuring. So you can get 180-degree phase shifts rarely for purely technical reasons.

Response (*edited oral response*): Yes, it's true that some pixels erroneously show this half-cycle phase difference, but this error is not present when local maxima in the A-Scan spectra are selected for displacement tracking. The phase shift is generally due to signal competition between multiple pixels as shown by Nathan Lin and Lisa Olson. We make sure to only track local maxima, so we don't believe this is affecting our data.